

ANTENNA DEVELOPMENT FOR LUNAR ROBOTIC EXPLORATION

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Abstract – Lunar caves are subterranean wide and long tubes that could potentially host a human base. One of the key points in the future exploration of these caves is the communication network, which will allow to transmit the scientific data from the interior of the cave to the Moon surface. To establish a reliable link, an omnidirectional antenna, circularly polarized, has been developed in this work. The field of view (FoV) of the antenna is $\pm 30^\circ$ in elevation from the horizontal plane. The designed antenna has 0 dB gain in this FoV. The design is based on a pagoda antenna, and a ground plane has been added in order to reduce the interference with the metallic structure of a future explorer robot. Vibration simulations and a vacuum-thermal cycle (TVAC) test has been carried out. Finally, the antenna has been measured inside lava tubes in Lanzarote to ensure that this antenna will establish the communication link for a large set of the possible orientations of a mobile robot and in several possible scenarios in a Lunar exploration mission, including non-line-of-sight situations.

I. INTRODUCTION

Lunar lava caves present a great opportunity to establish a permanent base on the Moon, because they can provide protection against micrometeorites and thermal stability [1,2]. It is expected that these long and wide caves will be explored by a robotic fleet [3,4]. This fleet will have to overcome different type of obstacles: bends, slopes, boulders, collapses, etc. One of the key

points in the future exploration of these caves is the communication network, which will maintain the coordination of the robots and will allow to transmit the scientific data from the interior of the cave to the Moon surface. A medium-data rate communications network is foreseen for this purpose.

The research team presenting this work has analysed the possible communication system, including both cave propagation and the most useful protocol for this future mission. The conclusion was that the deployment of a *mobile ad-hoc network* (known as MANET), based on the 802.11n protocol (or higher) at 2.4 GHz band, would meet the identified requirements. In this work, an antenna for communications in lunar caves has been developed in accordance with these requirements.

II. ANTENNA REQUIREMENTS

In this work, an antenna, suitable for these mobile explorers, is presented. The antenna requirements have been defined based on the analysis of the morphology of Earth analogues lava caves and based on specific propagation model for lava caves [5,6]. This model has been experimentally validated and could be used by the robot fleet to optimize the coverage area inside an unknown scenario (Fig.1 and Fig.2).

Fig. 1. Possible model for a lunar skylight and cave conduit.

To establish a reliable link, an omnidirectional antenna, circularly polarized has been proposed. The field of view (FoV) of the antenna shall be $\pm 30^\circ$ in elevation from the horizontal plane and the antenna gain in this FoV shall be greater than 0 dBi. The antenna bandwidth shall be greater than 100 MHz. On the other hand, the antenna operational temperature shall be between -20° to 60°C .

III. ANTENNA DESIGN

Fig.3 shows the developed antenna. This pagoda antenna follows the same radiation principles as a traditional cloverleaf antenna but applying the philosophy to a printed PCB form. To achieve this, there are two complementary PCB disks with arms facing opposite directions in order to generate circular polarization. A ground plane (baseplate) of the same size as the radiating discs has been included to reduce interference from the rover's radiation, which is still undefined. A small intermediate disc has been added to improve the antenna's adaptation to the selected band. Also a radome, manufactured with Polyetheretherketone (PEEK) has been included, to protect the antenna against either lunar dust or shocks.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3. a) Simulation model. b) Manufactured prototype.

Fig. 2. Analogue Lunar cave (La Corona lava tube in Lanzarote, Spain).

Fig. 4. shows the antenna gain measurements. The antenna presents very good radiation symmetry around Z-axis (symmetry axis), with a variation smaller than 1 dB in almost all cases. The antenna meets the gain requirement between $\theta=60^\circ$ to $\theta=110^\circ$, measured from the symmetry axis. Between $\theta=110^\circ$ and $\theta=120^\circ$ the antenna gain is better than -2 dB. In the whole FoV, the axial ratio of the antenna is less than 3 dB.

The antenna gain requirement is too demanding, because the structure of the robot on which the antenna is mounted will modify the radiation pattern, especially in the range $\theta=90^\circ$ to $\theta=120^\circ$. On the one hand, the requirement can be relaxed, or it can be maintained with the addition of a -3dB margin in the link budget. On the other hand, once the exploring rover is known, a second iteration in the design can improve the radiation in that angle range, but it is not guaranteed in the whole frequency band.

IV. ANTENNA NON FUNCTIONAL TESTS

A. Vibration Test

The mechanical concept for the antenna comprises three elements: the ground-plane, the assembly composed by the coaxial cable and the disks and the radome.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. Measured realized gain of the QM1 at 2.4 GHz (a) for different φ cuts and (b) for different θ cuts. RHCP in continuous line and LHCP in dashed lines.

The cable assembly is attached to the baseplate through a PEEK protector using hardened Araldite 138 AM glue and then this protector is attached to the cable with this same glue. Regarding strength analysis, the limiting union is the attachment between the base and the PEEK protector. This union was dimensioned to have enough resisting surface to cope with the random vibration. The disks are assembled on the cable by welding using copper.

A Finite Element Model was built following the simulated model. Although global dimensions were used, the complex geometrical shapes were substituted by flat surfaces, except for the cable that was represented as a solid 3D mesh, everything resulting in a simple Patran geometry (Fig. 5). The unions were modelled using two Rigid Body Elements (RBE2) with Multi-Point Constraints (MPCs) between the joint areas with a CBUSH to recover loads between the RBE2s. The mass of the model is 0.107 kg.

Our analyses shown that the margins are positive and mostly quite large. There are two points to keep track of in the next stages of the design: stress on the inner parts of the coaxial cable (margins are positive but close to zero) and the joint between the PEEK protector and the base. The first should be kept under check for

the future. However, that is a conservative number as the area of the union that leads to this stress is slightly

under-sized in the model in order not to provide excessive stiffness through the RBE2. More detailed modelling in the future should bring this value up. Regarding the second joint, if it is needed, the joint area could be further increased but at this point due to the very high safety factors it is not believed to be necessary. Therefore, the conclusion is that, from a structural point of view, the design will be able to accomplish the mission.

Fig. 5. Simulated antenna model. (Radome is not included in the picture)

B. Thermovacuum test

In order to validate the operational temperature (-20° to 60°C) requirement, a Thermo Vacuum Chamber (TVAC) test of the final prototype has been carried out.

The antenna was placed in the central part of the TVAC baseplate, and it is surrounded by electromagnetically absorber shroud made of Ecosorb. The antenna under test (AUT) is attached to the baseplate through the interface support shown in Fig. 6.a (copper part). Once the antenna-support-baseplate assembly was bolted, a total of 12 thermocouples were attached on the baseplate, the interface and the AUT. To understand the thermal environment during the tests, the temperature evolution with time is presented in Fig. 6.b.

Four thermal cycles have been carried out, measuring the reflection coefficient every two minutes. During these cycles, the antenna reflection coefficient was monitored. The results for the second cycle (as an example) are shown in Fig. 7. In all cases, the minimum of the reflection coefficient remains at 2.4 GHz, with small variations. The antenna bandwidth remains at $150\text{ MHz} \pm 10\text{ MHz}$, greater than the required bandwidth for this antenna (100 MHz).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6. a) Picture of the AUT and the test cap. at the TVAC. b) Time evolution of main temperatures of the TVAC tests

Fig. 7. Antenna reflection coefficient at the second cycle.

V. FUNCTIONAL TEST IN RELEVANT SCENARIOS

In this activity, the final prototype shall be measured in an analogue cave, as lava caves in Lanzarote. To do so, two different communications subsystems have been experimentally studied: one with only one port and a pagoda antenna, and a second one with 1x2 MIMO, using QY antennas, potentially with higher power consumption.

Fig. 8 shows one of the selected scenarios, in the La

Corona lava tube. This scenario allows us to measure situations with line of sight (LoS) and non-LoS (NLoS).

Fig. 8. Picture and sketch of one of the measurement scenario.

This scenario is a narrower corridor with two bends, which implies several points with NLoS. Six points has been selected, with different distances between transmitter and receiver.

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The conclusion of the measurement campaign shows that the amplitude of the received signal diminishes with the distance between transmitter and receiver, getting worse with NLoS situations. The behavior of the pagoda antenna is more stable than the one of the QY system.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Exploring lunar caves is a future challenge with great scientific value. For the development of this exploration mission, a communication network must be deployed. This work presents a pagoda antenna optimized for a future exploration rover. This antenna has circular polarization throughout its FoV ($\pm 30^\circ$ in elevation from the horizontal plane). The antenna gain is greater than 0 dBi between 30° and -20° . This value could be improved, once the exploration rover is known. It has been manufactured with space-appropriate materials, allowing it to successfully pass vibration analysis and thermal vacuum testing. Additionally, it has been measured inside terrestrial caves, analogous to lunar ones, showing that the communication system could use a single antenna instead of a MIMO system, thus saving mass and power.

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] F. Sauro et al., Lava tubes on Earth, Moon and Mars: A review on their size and morphology revealed by comparative planetology, *Earth-Science Rev.* 209 (2020) 103288. ISSN 0012-8252.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2020.103288>
- [2] L. Carrer et al., Radar evidence of an accessible cave conduit on the Moon below the Mare Tranquillitatis pit. *Nature Astronomy* (2024).
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41550-024-02302-y>
- [3] P. F. Miaja et al., RoboCrane: A system for providing a power and a communication link between lunar surface and lunar caves for exploring robots, *Acta Astronautica* 192 (2022), 30-46. ISSN 0094-5765.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2021.11.023>
- [4] A. D. Issa, et al., Moon Diver: Exploring a pit's exposed strata to understand lunar volcanism, *Acta Astronautica* 211 (2023) 163-176. ISSN 0094-5765.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2023.05.042>
- [5] G. Leon et al., Analysis of a communication network inside a lunar lava cave. *European Lunar Symposium 2024*. Dumfries, United Kingdom.
- [6] W. Walsh and J. Gao, "Communications in a cave environment," 2018 IEEE Aerospace Conference, Big Sky, MT, USA, 2018, pp. 1-8, doi: 10.1109/AERO.2018.8396606.

Fig. 3. Received power sweeping the ϕ angle by the pagoda antenna (a) and the QY system (b) in scenario La Corona tube.